

Development Of New Antibiotics Using Metal Doped Graphitic Carbon Nitride Composite

Ibrahim Muhammad¹ Abubakar Isah¹ and Jamilu Usman²

¹Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Sokoto State University, Along Birnin Kebbi Road, Sokoto, P.M.B. 2134, Nigeria.

²Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Membrane and Water Security (IRC-MWS), King Fahad University of Petroleum and Minerals, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia.

Corresponding Author: Ibrahim Muhammad

Abstract

Bacteria naturally develop resistance to antibiotics used in disease prevention and also transfer from one host to another. Despite the tremendous efforts done by many pharmaceutical industries during the past decades in producing various forms of antibiotics, there is still an increased in resistance to these drugs by the microorganisms which leads to an increase in healthcare costs and mortality rate. Here in, we focus on the synthesis and doping of graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) with metals to the corresponding metal doped graphitic carbon nitride (M-g-C₃N₄) and also on the application of the as-synthesized composite as an antibacterial agent. The graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) was synthesized from melamine via condensation and then converted to metal doped graphitic carbon nitride (M-g-C₃N₄) by treatment with different metal precursors (CoCl₂.6H₂O, CuCl₂.2H₂O, FeCl₂.XH₂O and ZnCl₂) to obtained Co-g-C₃N₄, Cu-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄, and Zn-g-C₃N₄ respectively. The resultant material was characterized using XRD, FTIR, and FESEM. The antibacterial assay of the composite was assessed against the standard laboratory strains of Staphylococcus aureus (gram +ve), Salmonella typhi (gram -ve), Escherichia Coli (Gram -ve) and Streptococcus pyogenes (gram +ve) using well diffusion method. The as-synthesized composite show a good antibacterial activity against the test organisms with zone of inhibition ranging between 2-19mm, 2-21mm, 2-21mm and 2-20mm of Co-g-C₃N₄, Cu-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄, and Zn-g-C₃N₄ respectively. These indicate that the as-synthesized composites have good potentials of developing new antibiotics which will help in reducing healthcare costs and mortality rate due to resistance of bacteria to already manufactured drugs.

Keywords: Metal doped, Graphitic Carbon Nitride, Antibiotics, Resistance, Composite

INTRODUCTION

Human health improvement is the main subject of discussion throughout the world. In this aspect, one of the most important challenges is bacterial infections. Pathogenic bacteria can transmit between hosts and resists drug treatments [1, 2]. Even though pharmaceutical industries have done many efforts to address this issue by producing various forms of antibiotics during the past decades, there is still an increased in resistance to these drugs by the microorganisms [3], hence the need to develop new drugs. In response to these challenges carbon nitrides belongs to a group of compounds that are polymeric in nature and can be obtained through replacement of the carbon atoms with nitrogen. Carbon nitride's abundant nitrogen content enhances its catalytic properties, its thermal and chemical stability ensure durability in various applications. The material's tunable band gaps allow for adjustable electronic properties. The unique properties of carbon nitride make it promising for antimicrobial applications and its surface chemistry can be tailored for potential biomedical uses, such as biosensing or drug delivery. Among different type of carbon nitride materials, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) has high electron-

density, basic surface functionalities, and hydrogen-bonding motifs due to the presence of plenty of N atoms and has been extensively studied in many fields like photo-catalysis and photo-electrochemical water splitting [4], CO₂ reduction [5], and photocatalytic degradation of pollutants [6]. Later on, it was widely studied as a versatile support for noble metals to accomplish photocatalytic hydroxylation of benzene, oxidation, and hydrogenation reactions, Suzuki and Sonogashira couplings, and Knoevenagel reaction because of its interesting electronic and optical properties [7]. Several functional groups such as amines, polyethyleneimine (PEI), hydrazine, boronic acid, and phenyl groups have also been tethered with g-C₃N₄ either by chemical grafting or physical impregnation for CO₂ capture, CO₂ reduction, water splitting to H₂ or even to enhance its photoluminescence and sensing properties [8, 9].

In addition to this, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) has also attracted great interest in the field of biomedicine due to its unique elemental composition and photoelectric features. Due to its carbon and nitrogen content, it possesses an outstanding biocompatibility, which makes it beneficial and suitable in the field of biomedicine. The fluorescent

characteristics of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ can be applied to biological imaging. Furthermore, its appropriate energy level (2.7 eV) can promote the deposition of electrons, making $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ useful for antibacterial materials and photodynamic therapy (PDT) [10]. Recently, graphitic carbon nitride has been found to have great antibacterial activity against pathogenic bacteria (*Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Escherichia coli*) in wastewater [11]. Also, nitrogen-plasma-treated $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ ($N\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) nanosheets were reported to have a lipid heads, thus, resulting in an excellent antibacterial activity [12]. Graphitic carbon nitride ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) has also been widely used as versatile material with applications in photocatalysis, biosensing, and water splitting, owing to its high stability, chemical versatility, electronic-rich structure and nontoxicity [13, 14]. The unique structural and electronic properties of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ can be attributed to the heptazine rings with pyridinic nitrogen groups in $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in which six nitrogen lone pair serves as electronic donors [15]. Hence, $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ has an impressive capability to entrap metal ions through metal – N interactions. It can provide a versatile platform to immobilize metal catalysts in its framework, which can restrain the leaching of metal ion and promote its internal charge transfer [16].

The utilization of nanomaterials in crafting innovative antibacterial agents has emerged as a pivotal approach to combat drug – resistance bacterial infections, with engineered nanomaterial's standing out as crucial candidates for the next generation of antibacterial agents [17-31]. This study synthesizes and evaluates the doping of graphitic carbon ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) using some selected transition metals (Co, Fe, Zn and Cu) to the corresponding metal doped graphitic carbon nitride ($M\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) and also on the application of the as-synthesized composite as an antibacterial agent. The graphitic carbon nitride ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) was initially synthesized from melamine via condensation and then converted to metal doped graphitic carbon nitride ($M\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) by treatment with different metal precursors ($\text{CoCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, FeCl_3 , ZnCl_2 and $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) to obtain $\text{Co}\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{Fe}\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{Zn}\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and $\text{Cu}\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ respectively as represented in (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1: Synthesis of metal-doped graphitic carbon nitride ($M\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) composite.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Melamine, Cobalt (II) Chloride, Zinc (II) Chloride, Ferric Chloride anhydrous, Copper (II) Chloride dihydride and all other solvents were obtained from LobaChemie and used as received. Mueller Hilton nutrient agar and broth were used for antibacterial analysis. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out using a Bruker diffractometer (D8 Advance, Davinci) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ rays ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The FTIR measurements was carried out on Bruker α - Eco - ATR IR spectrometer using ZnSe crystal in the wavenumber ranging from $400 - 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The morphology was observed with field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, JEOL JEM-2100Plus). The test organisms were obtained from the Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Sokoto State University Sokoto, Nigeria. The microorganisms were standard laboratory strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (gram +ve) and *Salmonella typhi* (gram -ve).

Synthesis of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$

To synthesize graphitic carbon nitride ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$), 20 g of melamine was taken in a crucible and covered completely to avoid escape of fine particles. The crucible was then transferred into a muffle furnace and heated at a temperature of $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 hours at a heating rate of 3 degree per minute. After cooling to normal room temperature, the resultant pale-yellow material was obtained and grounded very well into fine powder using mortar and pestle, weighed and transferred into container which was stored in a desiccator for further treatment.

Conversion of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ to $M\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$

To a mixture of methanol (25.0 mL) and graphitic carbon nitride (1.0 g) in a round bottom flask, 0.1 g of $\text{CoCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added and covered with foil paper supported by a masking tape to avoid vaporization of the solvent. The content in the flask was then be stirred for 24 hours at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and then centrifuge at 3000 rotation per minute (rpm) for 5 minutes, then wash thoroughly with ethanol to remove excess chloride ions to obtained the cobalt doped graphitic carbon nitride material ($\text{Co}\text{-}g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$). The material was dried in an air circulating oven for 24 hours at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, grounded to fine powder and then stored for further use. The same procedure was adopted for Zn, Fe and Cu doping using ZnCl_2 , FeCl_3 and $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as precursors respectively. In addition to these different concentrations of metals loading was used to obtain 5 %, 10 % and 20 % concentration of each metal on the graphitic carbon nitride. The resultant composite material was characterized using FTIR, XRD, and FESEM and also subjected to antibacterial activity test.

Antibacterial Tests

The antibacterial test was conducted using the well diffusion method described by [32]. The Nutrient Agar plates was prepared according to manufacturer's instruction and was allowed to solidify for 15 minutes at room temperature and incubated without inoculum for 24 hours at 37°C to ensure the sterility of the medium. The dilution ratio for Gram-positive bacteria and Gram-negative bacteria was 1:1000 and 1:5000, respectively, using normal saline water. The Nutrient Agar plates was flooded with 1 mL of the inoculum and the excess was removed using Pasteur pipette. Four wells (cups) of about 4 mm in diameter was cut on each Nutrient Agar plate using a sterile cork borer and the agar plugs was removed using sterile ampoule file. The composite solution (0.5 mL) was placed in each of the wells and allowed to settle for two hours at room temperature before incubation for 24 hours at 37°C. The inhibition zone was observed and then recorded in millimetres using a transparent ruler. Standard antibiotic (Amoxicillin) was used as reference.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

This was carried out as described by [33]. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) was defined as the lowest concentration where no visible turbidity would be observed in the test tubes. The MIC was determined for the micro-organisms that showed reasonable sensitivity to the test composites. In this test, the micro-organisms was prepared using the broth dilution technique. The stock composite concentration of 100 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, and 25 mg/mL were made by dissolving 0.5 g, 0.25 g and 0.125 g of the composite in 5 ml of sterile distilled water and the working concentrations prepared by two-fold serial dilution technique that ranged from 0.098 mg/mL to 50 mg/mL using nutrient broth and later inoculated with 1.0 mL suspension of the test organisms. After 24 hours incubation at 37°C, the tubes were observed for turbidity. The lowest concentration where no turbidity is observed was taking and noted as the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC).

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimal bactericidal concentration was determined from broth dilution test resulting from the MIC tubes as described previously by inoculating the content of each test tube on a nutrient agar plate. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The lowest concentration of the composite that showed no growth was noted and recorded as the minimum bactericidal concentration [34].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Materials characterization

The crystallinity of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{Zn-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{Fe-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, and $\text{Cu-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ were determined using powder X-ray diffraction (see Figure 1 – 4).

The pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ shows a peak of high intensity at 27.4° that correspond to (002) plane, which is due to the interlayer-stacking of graphite [35]; whereas other peak that clearly appears at 13.1° with very low intensity corresponds to (100) plane and is assigned to the motif structural packing of in-plane tris-triazine. The X-ray diffraction results indeed confirm the high stability of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ toward functional group modification.

The XRD graph of $\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ as shown in figure 1, the reduced intensity of the main characteristic (002) peak reflection may indicate a decrease in crystallinity or an increase in lattice defects which can be attributed to the distortion of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ crystal cell after Co doping [36, 37]. Furthermore, no detectable peaks were observed corresponding to metallic cobalt [38], which could be due to low concentration of cobalt doping and homogeneous distribution across the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sample [39, 40].

Figure 1: XRD patterns of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ doped with various amount of Cobalt

The figure 2 graph below showed the conversion of $\text{Zn-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ as the intensity of the (002) peak decreases with increasing Zn content, indicating deterioration of crystallinity upon doping [41]. The intensity of the (100) peak plane also decreases upon Zn doping, this may indicate a strong interaction between $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ host and Zn species, which distorts the structure of nitride pores and alters the hole-to-hole distance. However even at highest doping level, the crystallinity of $\text{Zn/g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ is retained and no spurious phases are observed such as Zn, or chlorides [42, 43]. This indicates that the Zn species were chemically coordinated with the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ host and the graphitic – like structure was retained after Zn doping.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ doped with various amount of Zinc

It is clearly shown in figure 3 for Fe-g-C₃N₄, that the intensity of the (002) peak decreases with the doping of Fe. This suggests that adding Fe can limit the crystal growth of g-C₃N₄, the decrease in peak intensity can be attributed to an interaction between Fe and g-C₃N₄. This effect deforms the nitride pore structure and changes the distance between the holes [44]. In addition, the decrease in crystallinity in the (002) crystal planes can be attributed to the effects of Fe additions on the thermal condensation of melamine [45]. When the XRD graph was properly examined, no diffraction peak was observed for the Fe structure.

Figure 3: XRD patterns of g-C₃N₄ doped with various amount of Iron

On conversion to Cu-g-C₃N₄ as shown in figure 4, the intensity of (100) and (002) peak planes in the Cu-doped g-C₃N₄ sample indicated an improved crystallinity relative to undoped g-C₃N₄. No powder XRD peaks corresponding to Cu – metal was detected as expected due to the low Cu loading. Nevertheless, a slight shifting of (002) peak to a lower 2 theater angle was observed for Cu – doped g-C₃N₄ sample, which suggested some modification of the graphitic stacking of g-C₃N₄ as a consequence of Cu doping resulting in an increased interlayer distance [46]. However, varying the Cu dopant does not result in any significant differences in the diffraction patterns.

Figure 4: XRD patterns of g-C₃N₄ doped with various amount of Copper

The FTIR spectra of pure and modified samples are shown in figure 5. The broad peak absorption observed at 2900 – 3400cm⁻¹ is due to the presence of N–H stretching vibration [47]. The peaks observed between 1100 – 1700cm⁻¹ are characteristics peaks of tris-s-triazine assigned to C=N and C–N heterocyclic aromatic rings units as observed in the case of XRD [48]. The intensity of these peaks decreases with increasing metal content (i.e Zn, Fe, Co or Cu), suggesting that g-C₃N₄ contains numerous triazine rings that comprise Sp² C–N bond such as N=C–N and C–N=C. However, the graphitic structure of g-C₃N₄ was partly damage by metal doping. In particular, some triazine units were broken by deamination upon metal precursor addition. All these results imply that the g-C₃N₄ frame work partly changed upon metal doping. Some triazine rings were broken and Sp² C–N bonds were transformed into C ≡ N triple bonds [49, 50].

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of g-C₃N₄, Co-g-C₃N₄, Zn-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Cu-g-C₃N₄

We further investigated the morphological features with scanning electron microscope (SEM) and EDX. Scanning electron microscope of pristine graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄), cobalt-doped graphitic carbon nitride (Co-g-C₃N₄), zinc-doped graphitic carbon nitride (Zn-g-C₃N₄), iron-doped graphitic carbon nitride (Fe-g-C₃N₄), and copper-doped graphitic carbon nitride (Cu-g-C₃N₄) materials showed rod-like morphology (Figure 6a-e); the particle size of pristine material was found to be between 1–8 μm in length with about 150–135 nm thickness; whereas the post-synthetically modified Co-g-C₃N₄, Zn-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄, and Cu-g-C₃N₄ composites were to be in the range of 1–6 μm in length. The morphological features were further investigated using EDX, the presence of C, N, Co, Zn, Fe and Cu in the pure g-C₃N₄ and modified g-C₃N₄ samples can be confirmed using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDX). The results of EDX analysis (Figure 6f – j) unambiguously indicated the presence

of cobalt, zinc, iron and copper on the surface of the M-g-C₃N₄ catalyst.

Figure 6: SEM Images of (a) g-C₃N₄ (b) Co-g-C₃N₄ (c) Zn-g-C₃N₄ (d) Fe-g-C₃N₄ (e) Cu-g-C₃N₄ and EDX images of

Antibacterial Activity of g-C₃N₄, Co-g-C₃N₄, Zn-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Cu-g-C₃N₄

After characterizing the g-C₃N₄, Co-g-C₃N₄, Zn-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Cu-g-C₃N₄, the efficacy of the composite was investigated against standard laboratory strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (gram +ve) and *Salmonella typhi* (gram -ve). Table 1(a)-(e) show the details of the results obtained from the antibacterial activity test of pure g-C₃N₄, Co-g-C₃N₄, Zn-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Cu-g-C₃N₄ composite and the standard antibiotic (Ampicillin).

Table 1(a) below show the detailed of the antibacterial activity of cobalt doped graphitic carbon nitride (Co-g-C₃N₄), the pure g-C₃N₄ shown no activity on all the bacterial strains while Co-g-C₃N₄ has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 2.00-19.00 mm of various loading concentrations.

Table 1(a): Antibacterial activity of cobalt doped graphitic carbon nitride (Co-g-C₃N₄)

Metal loading	Concentration (mg/mL)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>
5 %	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	4.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	4.00
10 %	25.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00
	50.00	4.00	0.00	12.00	8.00
	100.00	8.00	8.00	16.00	12.00
20 %	25.00	4.00	2.00	12.00	4.00
	50.00	8.00	4.00	16.00	12.00
	100.00	12.00	10.00	19.00	15.00
g-C ₃ N ₄	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 1(b) below show the detailed of the antibacterial activity of copper doped graphitic carbon nitride (Cu-g-C₃N₄), the pure g-C₃N₄ shown no activity on all the bacterial strains while Cu-g-

C₃N₄ has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 2.00-21.00 mm of various loading concentrations.

Table 1(b): Antibacterial activity of copper doped graphitic carbon nitride (Cu-g-C₃N₄)

Metal loading	Concentration (mg/mL)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>
5 %	25.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	0.00
	50.00	4.00	0.00	6.00	0.00
	100.00	6.00	5.00	8.00	2.00
10 %	25.00	4.00	6.00	8.00	4.00
	50.00	8.00	7.00	10.00	8.00
	100.00	14.00	10.00	12.00	12.00
20 %	25.00	7.00	12.00	12.00	10.00
	50.00	10.00	16.00	18.00	12.00
	100.00	20.00	18.00	21.00	19.00
g-C ₃ N ₄	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 1(c) below show the detailed of the antibacterial activity of iron doped graphitic carbon nitride (Fe-g-C₃N₄), the pure g-C₃N₄ shown no activity on all the bacterial strains while Fe-g-C₃N₄

has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 2.00-21.00 mm of various loading concentrations.

Table 1(c): Antibacterial activity of iron doped graphitic carbon nitride (Fe-g-C₃N₄)

Metal loading	Concentration (mg/mL)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>
5 %	25.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	0.00
	50.00	2.00	0.00	4.00	2.00
	100.00	4.00	0.00	6.00	4.00
10 %	25.00	6.00	0.00	7.00	6.00
	50.00	9.00	0.00	10.00	8.00
	100.00	13.00	4.00	12.00	11.00
20 %	25.00	14.00	8.00	13.00	14.00
	50.00	16.00	14.00	15.00	17.00
	100.00	18.00	20.00	21.00	20.00
g-C ₃ N ₄	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 1(d) below show the detailed of the antibacterial activity of zinc doped graphitic carbon nitride (Zn-g-C₃N₄), the pure g-C₃N₄ shown no activity on all the bacterial strains while Zn-g-C₃N₄ has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 2.00-20.00 mm of various loading concentrations.

Table 1(d): Antibacterial activity of zinc doped graphitic carbon nitride (Zn-g-C₃N₄)

Metal loading	Concentration (mg/mL)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>
5 %	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	4.00
10 %	25.00	4.00	5.00	7.00	10.00
	50.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	12.00
	100.00	10.00	10.00	12.00	14.00
20 %	25.00	13.00	12.00	14.00	15.00
	50.00	14.00	16.00	16.00	17.00
	100.00	16.00	18.00	19.00	20.00
g-C ₃ N ₄	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 1(e) below show the detailed of the antibacterial activity of standard antibiotic (Ampicillin) which has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 15.00-22.00 mm.

Table 1(e): Antibacterial activity of standard antibiotic (Ampicillin)

Antibiotic Concentration	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>
Ampicillin (50 mg/mL)	15.00	15.00	21.00	22.00

The above result shows that pure g-C₃N₄ has no antibacterial activity on all test organisms. The results deduced that Co-g-C₃N₄, Cu-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Zn-g-C₃N₄ has activity on all the bacterial strains with zone of inhibition ranging from 2.00-21.00 mm. The Co-g-C₃N₄ and Zn-g-C₃N₄ composite a good antibacterial activity on all the test organisms at concentration of 25 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL and 100 mg/mL at various loading (5%, 10% and 20%) with

zone of inhibition ranging between 2.00 mm to 19.00 mm (Table 1a and 1d). The Cu-g-C₃N₄ and Fe-g-C₃N₄ composite exhibited excellent antibacterial activity on all the test organisms with zone of inhibition ranging between 2.00 mm to 21.00 mm (Table 1b and 1c). The Co-g-C₃N₄ composites showed a high level of activity on gram positive bacteria than gram than gram negative bacteria (Table 1a). The Cu-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Zn-g-C₃N₄ composite showed a high

level of activity on both gram-negative bacteria and gram-positive bacteria, but all the organisms were found to be susceptible. The results when compared with Amoxicillin (Standard Antibiotic – Table 1e), the zone of inhibition produced by the antibiotic against the test organisms was found to be very appreciable in relation to those activities produced by the composite under study. Furthermore, according to [51] diameter of zones of inhibition ≥ 10 mm are considered active. The as-synthesized composites (Co-g-C₃N₄, Cu-g-C₃N₄, Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Zn-g-C₃N₄)

were subjected to MIC and MBC determination (Table 1f - i).

The results of MIC and MBC in table 1(f) below shows that Co-g-C₃N₄ composite have an MIC of 100 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 50.00 mg/mL on both *E. Coli*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus* and the MBC obtained 100 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 55 mg/mL on *S. typhi*, 50 mg/mL on both *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*.

Table 1(f): Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of cobalt doped graphitic carbon nitride (Co-g-C₃N₄)

Test Organism	MIC (mg/mL)	MBC (mg/mL)
<i>E. coli</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. typhi</i>	50.00	55.00
<i>S. aureus</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	100.00	100.00

The results of MIC and MBC in table 1(g) below showed that Cu-g-C₃N₄ composite have an MIC of 100 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 55.00 mg/mL on *S. aureus*, 50.00 mg/mL on both *E. coli* and *S. typhi* and

MBC obtained 100 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 50.00 mg/mL on both *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus*

Table 1(g): Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of copper doped graphitic carbon nitride (Cu-g-C₃N₄)

Test Organism	MIC (mg/mL)	MBC (mg/mL)
<i>E. coli</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. typhi</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. aureus</i>	55.00	50.00
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	100.00	100.00

The results of MIC and MBC table 1(h) below showed that Fe-g-C₃N₄ composite have an MIC of 100.00 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 55.00 mg/mL on *S. aureus*, 50.00 mg/mL on both *E. coli* and *S. typhi*,

and MBC obtained 100.00 mg/mL on *S. pyogenes*, 50.00 mg/mL on both *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, and *S. aureus*.

Table 1(h): Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of iron doped graphitic carbon nitride (Fe-g-C₃N₄)

Test Organism	MIC (mg/mL)	MBC (mg/mL)
<i>E. coli</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. typhi</i>	50.00	50.00
<i>S. aureus</i>	55.00	50.00
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	100.00	100.00

The results of MIC and MBC table 1(i) below showed that Zn-g-C₃N₄ composite have an MIC of 100 mg/mL on both *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus* and *S.*

pyogenes, and MBC obtained 100 mg/ml on *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenes*.

Table 1(i): Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of zinc doped graphitic carbon nitride (Zn-g-C₃N₄)

Test Organism	MIC (mg/mL)	MBC (mg/mL)
<i>E. coli</i>	100.00	100.00
<i>S. typhi</i>	100.00	100.00
<i>S. aureus</i>	100.00	100.00
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	100.00	100.00

CONCLUSION

We have described a simple and efficient method of doping graphitic carbon nitride g-C₃N₄ to corresponding (M-g-C₃N₄) by treating the graphitic carbon nitride g-C₃N₄ with metal precursors (CoCl₂.6H₂O, FeCl₃, ZnCl₂, and CuCl₂.2H₂O). The as-synthesized composite was characterized using XRD, FTIR, SEM and EDX and the results shows

that the graphitic carbon nitride g-C₃N₄ retain its structural integrity even after doping with different metals. The evaluation of antibacterial activity of the M-g-C₃N₄ composite using some selected bacterial strains (*Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (gram +ve) and *Salmonella typhi* (gram -ve)) was found to be appreciable when compared with the

standard antibiotic (Ampicillin). The results were found to be very useful in academics and can be extended to pharmaceutical applications as well. These findings have significant implications for addressing the growing threat of antibiotic resistance.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict to be declared

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